

The Verification Crisis: Expert Perceptions of GenAI Disinformation and the Case for Reproducible Provenance*

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Abstract

The growth of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) has shifted disinformation production from manual fabrication to automated, large-scale manipulation. This article presents findings from the first wave of a longitudinal expert perception survey (N=21) involving AI researchers, policymakers, and disinformation specialists. It examines the perceived severity of multimodal threats – text, image, audio, and video—and evaluates current mitigation strategies.

Results indicate that while deepfake video presents immediate “shock” value, large-scale text generation poses a systemic risk of “epistemic fragmentation” and “synthetic consensus,” particularly in the political domain. The survey reveals skepticism about technical detection tools, with experts favoring provenance standards and regulatory frameworks despite implementation barriers.

GenAI disinformation research requires reproducible methods. The current challenge is measurement: without standardized benchmarks and reproducibility checklists, tracking or countering synthetic media remains difficult. We propose treating information integrity as an infrastructure with rigor in data provenance and methodological reproducibility.

CCS Concepts

• **Computing methodologies** → **Artificial intelligence**; • **Security and privacy** → *Social aspects of security and privacy*.

Keywords

Verification crisis, reproducible provenance, GenAI disinformation, expert perception, epistemic fragmentation, synthetic consensus, computational reproducibility, deepfake detection, C2PA, Methods Hub

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1 Introduction

The digital information ecosystem faces a structural shift in the economics of deception—a *verification crisis* [16, 30]. The maturation and accessibility of Large Language Models (LLMs) and diffusion-based image generation have reduced the marginal cost of producing high-fidelity disinformation toward zero [17, 18, 23]. We observe a transition from “disinformation as a craft”—characterized by labor-intensive troll farms, manual image manipulation, and human-operated botnets—to “disinformation as an industry.” This industrial mode enables automated, personalized, and persistent synthetic content at scale [10]. Such a shift risks eroding the shared factual basis that underpins democratic deliberation, scientific discourse, and social cohesion—a phenomenon we term *epistemic fragmentation*.

This paper examines this emerging threat through expert perspectives. By surveying AI engineers, policymakers –including members of the European Commission–, and academic researchers ($n = 21$), we map the GenAI threat landscape as perceived by practitioners. However, identifying the threat is insufficient. As our respondents observe, the traditional detection-versus-generation dynamic is failing [19]. Generative capabilities advance faster than detection methods, and defensive tools remain opaque, unverified, and short-lived.

This paper argues that the solution lies in the rigorous application of reproducible science. The “black box” nature of commercial GenAI models, combined with the opacity of social media algorithms, creates a “reproducibility crisis” in disinformation studies [20, 27]. If researchers cannot reproduce the generation of a threat or the performance of a detector, policy interventions become speculative and potentially harmful.

This paper integrates computational reproducibility checklists as proposed by Momeni, Khan, Kiesel, and Ross-Hellauer [22], reusable method repositories like the Methods Hub advocated by Bleier et al. [2], and structured knowledge graphs for tracking claims as developed by Dessi et al. [7–9]. The survey data indicate that experts favor *reproducible provenance*—transparent, standardized infrastructure for verifying information origins—over opaque detection systems.

1.1 Contributions: A Three-Act Narrative

This paper tells the story of a **Crisis of Verification** through three acts:

- (1) **Act I: The Industrialization of Lying.** We examine how experts perceive the varying risks of text, audio, image, and video modalities. The data show that experts are concerned not

only with *content* but also with *volume* and *personalization*. AI-generated text (Mean 6.1/7) poses a systemic risk by polluting everyday discourse, while Deepfake Video (Mean 6.4/7) attracts attention but is more readily debunked.

- (2) **Act II: The Failure of the Black Box.** We analyze why technical detection receives low confidence ratings (mean effectiveness $\approx 3.4/7$). Commercial detection systems are failing because they are *black boxes*. Experts rate them as the least effective strategy. This reflects a failure of reproducibility: if we cannot verify how a detector works, we cannot trust its claims.
- (3) **Act III: Reproducible Resistance** To survive this crisis, we need “Civil Engineering for Truth”—standardized, reproducible protocols. We introduce Momeni’s Checklists [22] and Bleier’s Methods Hub [2] as the necessary infrastructure to build valid detectors and verify provenance.

This paper argues for aligning computational social science with principles of rigor, reproducibility, and reusability. The ongoing expert survey is available at <https://github.com/aloth/verification-crisis>.

2 Theoretical Framework: Reproducible Resistance and the Science of Truth

To contextualize our survey findings, we situate them within the framework of computational reproducibility and web data analysis.

2.1 The Reproducibility Imperative in Social Data

The analysis of digital behavioral data has historically been plagued by a lack of standardization. “One-off” scripts, inaccessible datasets, and undocumented parameters render much of the research in this field ephemeral. As noted by Bleier et al. [2] regarding the Methods Hub initiative, enabling reproducible and user-friendly computational tools is essential for the maturation of computational social science. The Methods Hub serves as a centralized repository where researchers can find open-source, quality-tested, and reproducible methods for data collection and analysis.

This infrastructure matters because our survey respondents call for “society-wide infrastructure for provenance” and note that “coordination is a massive challenge.” The fragmented nature of current detection tools—often proprietary or undocumented—prevents cumulative knowledge building. Schoch et al.’s work on defining computational reproducibility—categorizing it by form, completeness, and availability [27]—provides the taxonomy needed to audit these tools. If a detection algorithm cannot be containerized and re-executed on a new dataset, it functions as a black box rather than a scientific instrument.

2.2 Benchmarking and Checklists: The Momeni-Khan Framework

Momeni, Khan, Kiesel, and Ross-Hellauer [22] have established the necessity of checklists for computational reproducibility in social sciences. Their work addresses the “validity gap” in computational methods. This framework is critical when analyzing our survey results regarding technical detection tools. Experts rated these tools as unreliable (mean effectiveness $\approx 3.4/7$). A primary reason cited

is the lack of standardized evaluation; detection claims are often made on static datasets that do not reflect the adversarial reality of the web.

Adopting the Momeni-Khan checklist approach for disinformation detection papers would ensure that claims of “99% detection accuracy” are reproducible and robust against real-world shifts in generative models. These checklists require researchers to document the exact versions of libraries, the seeds of random number generators, and the provenance of training data. In the context of GenAI, where a model update can render a detector obsolete overnight, such rigor is not optional—it is the only way to maintain epistemic security.

2.3 Knowledge Graphs and Longitudinal Tracking

The work of Dessi and colleagues on knowledge graphs, the Telescope dataset [8], and ClaimsKG [7] addresses the “epistemic fragmentation” identified by our survey respondents. One expert noted, “The risk is not just ‘fake news’ but interactive, personalized persuasion at scale.” To counter this, we need structured ways to map narratives across platforms. The investigation of fact-checking characteristics and biases [9] and longitudinal analysis of Telegram discourse [8] provide the architectural blueprint for the “AI-assisted verification” tools requested by respondents.

Furthermore, Khan’s research on characterizing digital behavioral traces [12], online computational reproducibility [13], and multilingual fact-checking [26] addresses the “vernacular gap” highlighted by survey respondents from the Global South. Recent work on Urdu fake news detection [24] exemplifies the kind of language-specific, reproducible research that must be scaled to combat global disinformation. The focus on reproducibility of these NLP pipelines ensures that detection models are not just biased towards high-resource languages like English but are robust across linguistic contexts. We cannot fight dynamic AI agents with static blocklists; we need dynamic, interconnected knowledge bases and reproducible NLP pipelines.

2.4 Paper Structure

The remainder of this paper is structured to follow our three-act narrative: Section 3 describes our survey methodology. Section 4 presents **Act I** (The Industrialization of Lying) and **Act II** (The Failure of the Black Box) through our survey findings on threat perceptions and mitigation skepticism. Section 5 presents **Act III** (The R2CASS Solution), discussing how reproducible infrastructure can address the crisis. Section 6 synthesizes the argument and calls for action.

3 Methodology

3.1 Recruitment and Sampling

The study employed a purposive snowball sampling strategy to recruit experts with direct experience in disinformation research, AI development, or digital policy. Initial recruitment seeds were identified through three channels: (1) **LinkedIn** searches for roles such as “Trust and Safety Lead” and “AI Policy Director”; (2) **Google Scholar** identification of authors with highly-cited papers (> 100

citations) on deepfakes and neural fake news (2023–2025); and (3) speakers at relevant **conference proceedings** (e.g., ICWSM, ACM CCS). This process yielded a final cohort of $N = 21$ experts, including members of the European Commission, executives at AI laboratories, and senior academics. Data collection occurred between July and December 2025.

- **Sample Size:** $N = 21$ senior experts. Given the purposive sampling of high-level decision-makers (including a Member of the European Commission and executives at major AI companies), this sample prioritizes depth of insight over statistical power.
- **Respondent Verification:** All participants confirmed they were 18+ and consented to the study.
- **Geographic Distribution:** The sample is predominantly European, reflecting the region’s leadership in digital regulation (e.g., the AI Act):
 - European Union (EU): 52.4%
 - North America (USA & Canada): 23.8%
 - Europe (non-EU): 14.3%
 - South & Central Asia: 4.8%
 - East & Southeast Asia: 4.8%

3.2 Survey Instrument Design

The survey, hosted on Google Forms (<https://forms.gle/BCwYFtfxmZewkL97>), was designed to measure two latent constructs: *Threat Severity* and *Mitigation Efficacy*.

3.2.1 Threat Severity Scale. Respondents rated four modalities (Text, Image, Audio, Video) on a 7-point Likert scale.

- **Anchor 1 (Not a threat):** “The modality poses no significant risk beyond pre-GenAI baselines; current defenses are adequate.”
- **Anchor 7 (Severe threat):** “The modality poses a severe risk to information integrity, with potential for widespread epistemic harm.”

3.2.2 Mitigation Efficacy Scale. Respondents evaluated five strategies (Literacy, C2PA, Regulation, Platforms, Detection).

- **Anchor 1 (Not effective):** “The strategy is easily bypassed, technically unfeasible, or counter-productive.”
- **Anchor 7 (Very effective):** “The strategy provides a robust, scalable, and enduring defense.”

3.3 Participant Demographics

The respondent pool includes professionals with backgrounds in both technical and policy domains.

Experience Levels. Respondents reported substantial professional experience:

- 35 Years: Technologist / Web Standards Advocate
- 28 Years: Member of the European Commission
- 25 Years: Journalist; Investor/VC
- **Median Experience:** ≈ 15 Years

Technical Literacy.

- **LLM Understanding:** 90.5% rated their understanding of Large Language Models as 4 or higher (out of 7). 28.6% rated it 7 out of 7.

- **Deepfake Familiarity:** 42.9% rated their familiarity with deepfake technology 7 out of 7.

3.4 Qualitative Analysis Protocol

Qualitative responses were analyzed using *Reflexive Thematic Analysis* following the six-phase framework established by Braun and Clarke (2006; 2021) [3, 4].

- (1) **Inductive Coding:** We adopted a data-driven approach, avoiding pre-existing codebooks to allow GenAI-specific concepts (e.g., “Weaponized Intimacy”) to emerge from the data.
- (2) **Theme Generation:** Initial codes such as [volume], [personalized persuasion], and [consensus fabrication] were grouped under the higher-order theme of “Synthetic Consensus.” Similarly, codes regarding [detection failure] and [arms race] were grouped under “The Failure of the Black Box.”
- (3) **Refinement:** Themes were reviewed against the quantitative data to ensure consistency. For instance, the qualitative theme of “provenance as infrastructure” corresponds to the high quantitative rating for C2PA.

3.5 Data Analysis Method

Quantitative data regarding threat levels (1–7 scale) and mitigation effectiveness (1–7 scale) were analyzed using descriptive statistics to identify central tendencies and variance. Given the $N = 21$ sample size, statistical significance testing was deprioritized in favor of identifying strong signals and consensus clusters.

Qualitative responses from open-ended questions were coded thematically using an inductive approach. We identified recurring concepts such as “trust erosion,” “provenance,” “institutional failure,” and “epistemic fragmentation.” These qualitative insights were then mapped against the quantitative data to explain why certain trends appeared (e.g., why detection is rated low despite high technical literacy).

Reproducibility Statement. In adherence to R2CASS principles, the anonymized CSV dataset, the full survey instrument, and the Python/Pandas analysis code used to generate the statistics in this paper will be made available via the GESIS Methods Hub [2]. The reproducibility package follows the checklist guidelines established by Momeni et al. [22], documenting exact library versions, random seeds, and data provenance. This work builds on the JudgeGPT / RogueGPT research projects^{1,2}, which provide open-source infrastructure for studying human perception of AI-generated content.

4 Results: The Threat Landscape

The survey results indicate a threat landscape evolving faster than current defensive capabilities. Experts view GenAI disinformation not as a future risk but as a present problem.

4.1 Modalities of Deception: The Hierarchy of Harm

The survey asked experts to rate the threat level of four GenAI modalities: Text, Images, Audio, and Video. The results show a

¹<https://github.com/aloth/JudgeGPT>

²<https://github.com/aloth/RogueGPT>

Table 1: Participant Professional Roles and Experience

Role Category	Count	Representative Titles
AI Researchers / Engineers	9 (42.9%)	“VP @ social media company”, “Professor Cybersecurity”, “AI researcher”
Policymakers / Regulators	2 (9.5%)	“Member of the European Commission”, “Architect of DPI frameworks”
Journalists / Civil Society	3 (14.3%)	“Spiegel-Kolumnist”, “Disinformation/fact-checking professional”
Industry Executives	3 (14.3%)	“Exec of a leading AI company”, “Partner at an AI fund”
Other	4 (19.0%)	“Teacher”, “IT Architect”, “Ethicist/Legal Scholar”

high baseline of concern across all modalities, but with nuanced distinctions in how they threaten society.

Analysis. Deepfake Video is consistently rated highest (Mean 6.4) due to its “shock value” and the biological primacy of visual evidence—human beings are hardwired to believe what they see [28]. However, the qualitative data reveals a deeper anxiety regarding Text (Mean 6.1). While video is episodic (a specific deepfake goes viral), text is *systemic*. Text is the substrate of the internet—comments, reviews, news articles, tweets. Empirical studies on human perception confirm that LLM-generated text achieves near-human mimicry scores, making detection by readers unreliable [19, 20].

Experts warn that GenAI text generation allows for “Synthetic Consensus” or “Astroturfing” at an industrial scale. Prior research has shown that false news spreads faster and farther than true news online [29]. One respondent, a Professor of Cybersecurity, noted: “Large-scale text spambots (astroturfing)... have the most impact to our current information society.” Another expert, an AI researcher, emphasized: “Personalized 1:1 persuasion via text is a bigger threat to democracy than a fake video which can be debunked.” This distinction is critical: Video attacks the truth of an event, but text attacks the perception of public opinion. Research on the disinformation kill chain demonstrates a “perception-accuracy gap”—suspicion does not improve detection accuracy [19].

This aligns with Khan et al.’s work on digital behavioral data [12]. If the volume of synthetic text overwhelms organic human text, traditional social science methods that rely on scraping web data will fail. They will effectively be studying the output of LLMs rather than human behavior. Research on the disinformation kill chain demonstrates a “perception-accuracy gap”—suspicion does not improve detection accuracy [19]. This underscores the R2CASS mission: we need reproducible methods to filter and validate text data before it enters the social science pipeline.

4.2 Domain-Specific Threats: A Comparative Analysis

The survey segmented threats across Political, Health, Financial, and Social domains. While political threats are the most visible, other domains face significant risks that receive less attention.

4.2.1 The Political Domain: The Immediate Emergency. Respondents identified this domain as the primary vulnerability. 90.5% selected “Election interference via deepfake video” as a top-3 urgent risk.

“Democracy relies on a shared understanding of reality. When AI is used to manufacture consent or distort the

truth during elections, it attacks the sovereign will of the people.” (Member of the European Commission)

Interpretation. The experts differentiate between “content” and “reaction.” One respondent (VP at a social media company) noted, “The threat isn’t just the content, it’s the reaction to it... Election interference is a societal problem where our role is to give people context, not to censor speech.” This suggests that technical detection alone is insufficient; social science approaches to measuring impact—as advocated by Bleier and Schoch in their work on computational reproducibility in CSS [27]—are required to understand how disinformation changes voting behavior.

4.2.2 The Financial Domain: The Rise of Audio Fraud. While political threats are about persuasion, financial threats are about extraction. The rise of audio-cloning is a specific, high-velocity threat here.

“Voice-based payment scams are the new phishing.” (Cybersecurity Expert)

“Crypto and finance rely on cryptographic truth. AI attacks that foundation.” (FinTech Executive)

Interpretation. The “crypto-provenance” solution mentioned by a respondent highlights a potential intersection between Web3 technologies and R2CASS’s focus on data integrity. If financial markets cannot trust the voice on the phone, the friction in the economy increases drastically.

4.2.3 The Social Domain: Weaponized Intimacy. A notable finding is the emergence of “Weaponized Intimacy” or the “Psychosis Risk.”

“Looking ahead five years, a major, currently underestimated risk is ‘Weaponized Intimacy’ (Persuasive AI Companions). While we currently focus on deepfakes (fake content), the next frontier is deep agents (fake relationships).” (AI Ethics Researcher)

“The ‘Psychosis Risk.’ That millions of people will fall into deep, emotionally dependent relationships with AI companions that are manipulated by bad actors. Disinformation won’t just be a news article; it will come from your ‘best friend’ (the AI).” (Technology Executive)

Implication. This represents a shift from broadcasting lies to micro-targeting emotional manipulation. Studying this requires new, reproducible methodologies. Dessi’s TeleScope dataset [8], which looks at Telegram channels, is a perfect example of the kind of data needed. Telegram is often used for more intimate,

Table 2: Perceived Threat Level by Modality (Mean Rating / 7)

Modality	Mean	Key Expert Insight
Deepfake Video	6.4	“The ultimate tool for eroding the ‘shared objective reality’ required for democracy...It creates an environment of total doubt.”
AI-Generated Text	6.1	“Large-scale text generation is the most significant threat to eroding general veracity discernment... The marginal cost... is trending toward zero.”
Voice Cloning (Audio)	5.9	“Audio cloning presents an immediate, hard-to-detect vector for fraud... Voice-based payment scams are the new phishing.”
AI-Generated Images	5.8	“It helps calibrate public expectations. People need to understand that they can be fooled.”

Figure 1: Threat Perception Heatmap. Heatmap of expert threat ratings showing the concentration of high-severity concerns in the Political domain compared to the Social domain. Note the skew towards “Severe Threat” (7) for Political Text and Video.

community-based communication than Twitter/X. To study “deep agents,” researchers will need longitudinal datasets of interaction, not just static snapshots of posts.

4.3 The “Epistemic Fragmentation”

A recurring theme in the qualitative data is the fear that GenAI will destroy the possibility of knowing anything—a state of *Epistemic Fragmentation*.

“The risk is not that people believe a specific lie, but that they stop believing in the possibility of truth altogether.” (Policy Advisor)

“Epistemic fragmentation is more dangerous than any single fake video.” (AI Researcher)

“The ‘Dead Internet Theory’ is becoming reality. When 99% of content is synthetic, the remaining humans will

retreat into smaller, closed tribes to find truth.” (Journalist)

This “Reality Apathy” poses a challenge for the R2CASS community: If the “Web Data” we study is largely synthetic, our social science becomes a study of bot behavior. Bleier’s work on computational reproducibility [2] becomes the defensive wall against this, while structured approaches like ClaimsKG [7] provide the infrastructure for tracking claim truthfulness at scale. We must be able to prove that our datasets are human, or at least understand the synthetic distribution within them.

4.4 Mitigation Strategies: The Failure of Detection

The survey asked experts to rate and rank mitigation strategies. The results show low confidence in purely technical solutions, particularly detection tools.

Figure 2: Urgency Ranking. Top-3 Urgent Risks selected by experts, highlighting Election Interference (90.5%) and Text Spambots (61.9%) as the dominant concerns, far outpacing Phishing or Financial Fraud.

Table 3: Effectiveness Ratings of Mitigation Strategies (1–7 Scale)

Strategy	Mean	Primary Limitation Cited
Media / Public Literacy	4.8	“Reaches only tech-savvy audiences”; “Risks increasing general distrust”; “Impact fades once novelty wears off.”
Digital Watermarking / C2PA	4.2	“Easily bypassed by adversarial content” (e.g., stripping metadata); “Coordination... massive challenge.”
Government Regulation	4.1	“Pacing problem” (Laws are too slow); “Stifles open-source innovation”; “Europe is regulating itself out of relevance.”
Platform Enforcement	3.5	Business model conflict (“Platforms profit from engagement, not truth”).
Technical Detection Tools	3.4	“The ‘cat and mouse’ dynamic... detection becomes statistically harder”; “Unreliable.”

Figure 3: The Mitigation Gap. Best-Worst Scaling results indicating that Technical Detection Tools are viewed as the least effective strategy (38% rated “Least Effective”), contradicting the current industry focus on “AI catchers.” Provenance and Literacy are favored but face implementation hurdles.

4.4.1 *The Detection Paradox: Why “AI Catching AI” is Failing.* Experts view Technical Detection Tools as the least effective long-term solution (Mean 3.4). Prior work on neural fake news generation and detection has documented the inherent difficulty of this task [31]. A respondent explained:

“As models improve, detection becomes statistically harder... The ‘cat and mouse’ dynamic.” (AI Researcher)

Another noted:

“Ultimately, we need AI to detect AI. Humans won’t keep up. But detection is unreliable... it evokes the impression of reliability.” (Cybersecurity Expert)

R2CASS Relevance. This finding underscores the need for reproducible evaluation. Current commercial detectors are often “black boxes” with unpublished accuracy rates on novel datasets. When a new model (e.g., GPT-5) is released, existing detectors often fail. Moreover, recent work shows that adversarial perturbations can substantially degrade AI-generated text detection, making many detectors brittle against a determined adversary [11]. The community needs the checklists proposed by Momeni et al. [22] to audit these tools.

The Checklist Solution. Momeni’s framework requires detailing the training data, the preprocessing steps, and the evaluation metrics. If a detection paper claims high accuracy but does not provide these details (as is common), it contributes to the “illusion of reliability” that the experts fear. This is especially critical because detector performance can drop sharply when moving across datasets, generators, and post-processing pipelines, undermining real-world generalization [15]. R2CASS can lead the way by mandating these checklists for all submissions.

4.4.2 *The Provenance (C2PA) Hope & Skepticism.* While some experts see C2PA (Coalition for Content Provenance and Authenticity) as “essential infrastructure,” others note it creates a “two-tier internet.” Tools like Origin Lens [21] demonstrate that cryptographic verification of Content Credentials can be implemented on consumer devices, but adoption remains fragmented.

“Watermarking only works if everyone uses it. If ‘rogue’ open-source models do not implement these safety standards, the ecosystem remains polluted.” (Policy Advisor)

Tension. This highlights a tension between Open Science (which R2CASS supports) and AI Safety. Open weights allow for reproducibility, but also for the removal of watermarks. Recent advances in LLM watermarking [14] offer promise, but face similar adoption challenges. Bleier’s work on open science practices [2] suggests a middle ground: “Tiered Reproducibility,” where code is shared with trusted parties even if not fully public, could be applied to safety mechanisms.

4.4.3 *Literacy as an “Immune System.”* There is a split on media literacy. Some view it as the only viable defense:

“Literacy is the ‘user interface’ for truth.” (Journalist)

Others warn of “Skepticism Spillover”:

“It risks increasing general distrust... making people skeptical of all content.” (AI Ethics Researcher)

Recommendation. Literacy tools must be rigorous. Research on the psychology of fake news suggests that analytical thinking can reduce susceptibility to misinformation [25]. The mention of “gamification” and “inoculation” suggests a need for reproducible social science experiments to test which literacy interventions actually work. We cannot rely on intuition; we need reproducible studies, potentially hosted on the Methods Hub [2], to share effective literacy curricula.

5 Discussion: Toward a Reproducible Resistance

The survey data indicate a mismatch between threat scale and defense capacity. The threats are industrial, personalized, and multimodal, while defenses remain fragmented and easily bypassed. Experts call for structural change.

5.1 The Need for a “Methods Hub” for Disinformation

The varying perceptions of threat and mitigation effectiveness stem from a lack of shared data and methods. One expert noted:

“We need a global scientific agreement that certain safety features are mandatory.” (Technology Executive)

This is exactly the mission of the GESIS Methods Hub [2]. To address the “epistemic fragmentation,” we need a centralized, open-access repository where:

- (1) **Datasets of synthetic vs. organic content are curated and versioned.** The TeleScope dataset by Gangopadhyay, Dessi, Dimitrov, and Dietze [8] is a prime example. It provides a longitudinal view of Telegram, a platform rife with disinformation. By making this dataset available and citable, Dessi et al. allow the entire community to test detection hypotheses on real-world data, not just toy datasets.
- (2) **Detection Algorithms are hosted in reproducible containers** (Docker/Binder), allowing independent verification of their efficacy—addressing the “unreliable detection” concern raised by respondents.
- (3) **Reproducibility Checklists** [22] are applied to all new findings on AI influence, ensuring that policy is based on solid science, not hype.

5.2 Narrative Shift: From “Truth” to “Provenance”

The narrative for the final paper should pivot from the philosophical (and computationally intractable) goal of “Determining Truth” to the technical and reproducible goal of “Verifying Provenance.” The survey respondents repeatedly emphasized that they do not want AI to be the “arbiter of truth.” Instead, they want tools that show *context*: Where did this come from? Is it human?

Proposed Narrative Arc.

- (1) **The Diagnosis:** The survey confirms that GenAI has weaponized the “Information Gap” (asymmetry between generation cost and verification cost).

- (2) **The Failure:** Current ad-hoc detection fails because it is not robust or reproducible. It creates a false sense of security. Empirical validation shows that human detection accuracy degrades under sustained exposure to synthetic content [19].
- (3) **The Solution:** We must build “Epistemic Infrastructure” based on open standards. This involves integrating Knowledge Graphs [7] to track narrative evolution, Reproducible Workflows [2, 13] to audit defenses, and validated human perception benchmarks [20].

5.3 Operationalizing Reproducible Provenance

The expert consensus points away from *post-hoc* detection and toward *pre-hoc* provenance. However, to transition “provenance” from a theoretical ideal to a deployable infrastructure requires concrete metrics. We propose a framework integrating the C2PA technical standard with the reproducibility requirements of the Methods Hub.

5.3.1 Technical Metrics: The C2PA Standard. The Coalition for Content Provenance and Authenticity (C2PA) provides a cryptographic foundation for content authentication [5, 21]. To evaluate the readiness of this infrastructure, we propose the following metrics:

- **Manifest Robustness:** Defined as the survival rate of provenance assertions (signatures) after standard social media transcoding. Operational goal: > 95% survival of the c2pa box in ISO BMFF containers.
- **Verification Latency:** The computational overhead introduced by signature validation at the client side. To prevent user friction, this must remain < 100ms for static images and < 500ms for video streams [1].
- **Chain Continuity:** The percentage of an asset’s lifecycle (Capture → Edit → Publish) covered by unbroken cryptographic assertions.

5.3.2 Methodological Metrics: The TOM Score. Provenance applies not only to media but to the scientific tools used to study it. To address reproducibility concerns in disinformation detection, we adopt the *Transparency of Methods (TOM)* framework proposed by Momeni et al. [22]. We suggest that AI-based detection tools used in policy decisions should target a TOM Score > 0.8 on the Methods Hub checklist, documenting:

- (1) **Data Provenance:** Exact composition of Synthetic vs. Organic training data [2].
- (2) **Model Genealogy:** Full specification of the pre-trained base models (e.g., BERT, ViT) and fine-tuning hyperparameters.
- (3) **Adversarial Robustness:** Performance metrics against known adversarial attacks, not just static benchmarks.

Adopting these metrics shifts the discourse from abstract notions of “trust” toward measurable, auditable standards.

5.4 Future Risks: The “Psychosis Risk” and Human-AI Forensics

An emerging risk identified in the survey is *Anthropomorphism* or the “Psychosis Risk”; notably, empirical evidence suggests AI companions can reduce loneliness, which may help explain why some users become emotionally dependent on them [6]:

“Millions of people will fall into deep, emotionally dependent relationships with AI companions... Disinformation... will come from your ‘best friend’.” (Technology Executive)

This requires a new branch of computational social science: **Human-AI Interaction Forensics**. We need to develop reproducible methods to study how users bond with agents and how those bonds are exploited. This links back to Khan’s work on “Social Text-as-Data” [13]—we need to analyze the semantics of these human-AI conversations to detect manipulative patterns.

The challenge is considerable: How do we study relationships that are designed to be private and emotionally intimate? Traditional social science methods (surveys, experiments) may be insufficient. We may need new computational approaches that can analyze interaction logs at scale while preserving privacy—a perfect use case for the reproducible, containerized methods that R2CASS promotes.

6 Conclusion

This Work-In-Progress report documents expert perceptions of the emerging *verification crisis*: the era of “trusting your eyes” is ending, and verifying sources must take precedence. The survey results ($N = 21$) indicate that GenAI disinformation poses a multimodal threat to political and social discourse, driven by low production costs and detection difficulty. Experts identified “Epistemic Fragmentation” and “Synthetic Consensus” as primary concerns, with synthetic content risking displacement of human discourse.

However, the path forward is not simply “better AI models.” It is *better science*. The skepticism regarding current mitigation strategies—particularly technical detection—underscores the need for reproducible and reusable computational approaches. We cannot regulate or detect what we cannot consistently measure.

By adopting reproducibility checklists [22], Bleier and Khan’s Methods Hub [2, 13], and Dessi’s knowledge graphs and TeleScope dataset [7, 8] the research community can establish *reproducible provenance* as the foundation for countering GenAI disinformation.

As one respondent concluded:

“We must treat information integrity as infrastructure. Just as we build roads and power grids, we must build the protocols for truth verification.” (Policy Advisor)

Protocols must be defined, tested, and shared.

Ongoing Research. This paper presents findings from Wave 1 of our longitudinal study. We invite domain experts—AI researchers, policymakers, journalists, and cybersecurity professionals—to participate in Wave 2. The survey is available at <https://github.com/aloth/verification-crisis>.

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